

JURIDICAL SCIENCES

CONCEPTS OF THE CRIMINAL LIABILITY FOR CORRUPTION OFFENSES IN THE LEGISLATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The conceptual approach to the formation of the legal foundations of criminal liability in the Republic of Kazakhstan has undergone significant changes over time. In particular, a number of periods can be distinguished:

- the period from the 1990s to 2007, when the Law of the Republic No. 267-1, aimed at combating corruption, was put into effect, in 2001 the anti-corruption program for 2001-2005 was adopted for the first time.
- the period from July 2007 to the 2015 reform is the period of the anti-corruption strategy 2011-2015, and the adoption of some amendments to the criminal legislation, that is, until the period when more significant changes were made to the criminal legislation of the Republic in 2015.
- the period from 2015 to the current stage of development of legislation.

Keywords: criminal liability, corruption offences, anti-corruption legislation, Criminal Code.

1. At the first stage conditionally allocated by us, the legal approach in the regulation of criminal liability for corruption crimes was at the stage of its archaic development. In the legal structure of criminal legislation, only the first prerequisites were laid for the detailed regulation of criminal liability in this matter, state authorities are making only the first attempts to develop the concept of criminal liability for corruption in the activities of officials. The already mentioned Anti-corruption Law was adopted in 1998, which was a more or less detailed document regulating anti-corruption. By a President decree of 2001, this law was supplemented by the State anti-corruption program for 2001-2005 with an action plan, one of the goals of which was to improve the legal framework for combating corruption.

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan as of 2005 contained a fairly limited set of criminalized acts related to corruption. Criminal liability was provided for economic crimes, which, according to the legislator, may also be related to corruption, in particular, among them, the Criminal Code contained embezzlement of entrusted property (Article 176 of the Criminal Code), money laundering obtained by criminal means (Article 193 of the Criminal Code), economic smuggling (Article 209 of the Criminal Code). And a separate section provides for crimes that had a purely corrupt orientation as the main motive, in particular, they included abuse of official authority (Article 307 of the Criminal Code), abuse of power (Article 308 of the Criminal Code), mediation in bribery (Article 310 of the Criminal Code), forgery of official documents (Article 314 of the Criminal Code), non-fulfillment official powers (Article 315 of the Criminal Code), abuse of official powers (Article 380 of the Criminal Code).

Meanwhile, despite all the measures taken in terms of legislative regulation of the criminal law approach to the application of responsibility for corruption, a number of significant gaps and shortcomings in legal regulation, both at the organizational and substantive levels, are visible in the legislation of the period from 1990 to the 2000s:

- the details of the elements of crimes and criminal responsibility for the commission of acts of corruption are at this stage rather limited and fragmented, the proposed definitions of most corruption acts and, accordingly, criminal liability for their commission, significantly narrow the scope of influence on corrupt officials compared to the approach and standards proposed in the leading documents of the United Nations and the European Union, already existing at that time period;

- the elements of crimes in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan in the specified period are formulated insufficiently fully and expanded, for example, in the article on bribery, the subject of a bribe is reduced only to obtaining material benefits, and does not apply to obtaining non-monetary, non-material benefits and advantages;

- criminal liability for the promise of a bribe, extortion of a bribe is not provided for in certain compositions, and the commission of these actions is covered only within the framework of an attempt to commit a crime;

- there is no criminal liability for the commission of a crime in the form of bribery in favor of a third party;

- the system of punishments in the Criminal Code is inconsistent, on the one hand it is ranked and distributed depending on the severity of the crimes committed, and punishments reach up to 12 years in prison with forced confiscation of property for forms of passive bribery, but, on the other hand, sanctions for active bribery are represented only by the imposition of a fine and terms of imprisonment from three to five years of imprisonment, which hardly indicates their preventive and preventive properties;

- the statute of limitations for bringing to criminal responsibility for the commission of the most common forms of active bribery does not exceed two years, which is clearly disproportionate to the purposes and functions of the application of criminal responsibility, since crimes are very latent;

- the definitions of subjects given in the criminal legislation and in the legislative acts in force at that

time, which are subject to criminal liability and criminal prosecution, are sufficiently vague and require clarification of many features;

- the application of a number of measures of criminal legal impact, such as confiscation of property as an additional punishment, is weakly expressed and occurs at the discretion of the law enforcement officer and is only a mandatory measure in some cases;

- the criminal legislation of Kazakhstan does not involve bringing legal entities to criminal responsibility, unlike in European countries;

- the application of criminal liability is possible for the commission of active and passive forms of bribery in accordance with Articles 311-313 of the Criminal Code, but Article 313 provides for liability only for receiving a bribe in favor of the bribe-taker for committing actions in the interests of the bribe-taker or other persons represented by him, as well as for providing patronage or connivance in the commission of his actions, it also says about giving a bribe, and mediation in bribery, but it does not provide for criminal prosecution for extortion of a bribe and giving its promise or offering a bribe;

- inconsistently, the description of the bribe itself is given as a basis for criminal liability, so in Article 311 of the Criminal Code, the signs of a bribe characterize it as a form of "money, securities, other property, property rights, or material benefits", and Article 312 does not contain such characteristics, and simply mentions a bribe, the Criminal Code does not contain any other definitions of a bribe. Thus, criminal prosecution is possible only when committing acts of a corrupt nature that are associated with obtaining benefits of a property nature, and intangible assets or benefits are not covered by the concept of criminally punishable acts, which in general lags far behind international standards of criminal prosecution for bribery.;

- in the very law against corruption No. 267-1 of 02.07.1998. it contained article 13, listing acts that relate to obtaining benefits or advantages, that is, any remuneration in the form of money, services, in any form from any person; receiving gifts or services in connection with the performance of public functions, receiving invitations to travel for various purposes, and receiving other illegal benefits when obtaining loans, buying securities, property. But at the same time, this extensive system of bribes is not used as a basis for qualifying acts and bringing to criminal responsibility;

- Articles 311 and 312 of the Criminal Code of the period under study do not imply criminal prosecution for a bribe committed (transferred) in favor of third parties, only responsibility for receiving and giving a bribe in favor of persons equated in status to officials is provided, which in itself narrows the range of potentially punishable acts;

- the formal expression of criminal responsibility in the application of sanctions and punishments provided for in Articles 311 and 312 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of the period of the 2000s is an insufficiently balanced system. In particular, the inconsistencies and imbalance of criminal sanctions are expressed in the fact that for passive corruption activities (passive bribery), higher maximum penalties were provided, in

particular from 5 to 12 years in prison, and for active bribery – from 3 to 5 years in prison. Thus, such an obvious disproportionate differentiation of criminal responsibility could not serve the purposes of an effective and preventive impact on corruption manifestations;

- insufficient attention is paid to the collection and analysis of various analytical data and research on a transparent and transparent methodology based on international experience, which will allow more objectively to get an idea of the areas of corruption, its scale and impact on specific institutions of society and management, which in turn will optimize criminal liability measures for corruption;

- The legal system of Kazakhstan has not accepted the provisions of the leading conventions regarding criminal liability for corruption crimes, such as the UN Convention against Corruption of 2003, the Council of Europe Convention against Corruption of 1999.

2. At the second stage of the development of anti-corruption legislation in the republic, the programs of the strategic development plan of the republic were traditionally adopted, the UN Convention against Corruption of 2003 was ratified and legislative measures were taken to adapt and implement its provisions in Kazakhstan's anti-corruption legislation, the anti-corruption strategy for 2011-2015 was approved on 31.03.2011, and also adopted in the first reading amendments to the criminal law regarding the regulation of liability of legal entities for corruption offenses. There have been more noticeable changes in the concept of criminal liability for corruption crimes after amendments to the criminal law were made by the laws of 21.07.2007 and 07.12.2009, these amendments are aimed at implementing the provisions of the Istanbul Action Plan and recommendations. In particular, the following legislative measures were implemented:

- criminal liability was introduced for receiving a bribe by any official in favor of, or as a benefit addressed to third parties, and a certain inconsistency between the provisions of criminal and administrative legislation was eliminated.

- the application of criminal liability for corruption crimes has been expanded by including among its subjects persons who perform managerial functions in organizations with state participation with a share of at least 35% and the relevant provisions have been extended to national holding companies and other similar persons;

- the list of corruption crimes has been expanded, for which an additional penalty is applied in the form of confiscation of property;

- in addition, the law on countering the laundering (legalization) of criminally obtained funds and the financing of terrorism was put into effect;

- The Government of the Republic of Kazakhstan submitted to the Parliament a bill on the introduction of criminal liability of legal entities for corruption crimes, and it was approved in the first reading of the lower house of Parliament;

- the list of corruption crimes referred to in paragraph 5. of the Notes to Article 307 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan has been expanded

due to new compositions: the creation and/or management of a financial pyramid by a person authorized to perform state functions, or another person with a similar status, or related to the use of such a person of their powers; illegal acquisition of property by a person with official powers, performing the functions of state power, or a person with a similar status, or related to the use of his official powers by a person, as well as abuse of authority or improper exercise of authority, as well as inaction committed by officials from the military;

- sanctions were changed for some of the corruption crimes, the approach to their application was changed, in particular, such punishment as a fine, which was previously calculated as an amount equal to the total amount of wages received or other income of the accused person for a certain period of time, were excluded from criminal legislation;

- a number of general provisions of the criminal law on confiscation were supplemented with norms that extended confiscation also to the means and instruments of committing a crime;

- a provision was introduced prohibiting the use of imprisonment for crimes in the form of money laundering, obtained by criminal means, if the person who committed the crime voluntarily and fully reimburses all property damage caused to a citizen, organization or state, but with the exception of cases when it was committed by a person with authority, performing state functions, or by another person equated to him in status and is connected with the use of his official powers by such a person;

- the number of crimes for which there are no statute of limitations for criminal prosecution has been expanded, but at the same time corruption crimes have not been attributed to them, but only crimes against the order of management;

- Article 231 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan was clarified and amended, in particular, criminal liability was introduced for general assistance (patronage) and indulgence in office or official duties in return for providing illegal monetary remuneration or other assets, the composition of commercial bribery (bribery) on a large scale and especially large scale was also introduced.

Nevertheless, even at this stage, there have not been sufficiently serious changes in the scope of criminal liability, which is reflected in the absence of real effective measures aimed at bringing legislation and practice of its application in line with international standards.:

- criminal liability has not been introduced for the offer or promise of a bribe, as well as for accepting an offer or promise to give a bribe;

- there is no criminal liability for extortion of a bribe as a completed crime, and not as an attempt at a bribe, both in the public and private sectors of management;

- the concept of responsibility for bribery, including in the commercial sphere of management, in favor of third parties has not been formed;

- there is no formal approach to criminalizing influence trading;

- in criminal legislation, the concept of a bribe is not given at all, including its content is not disclosed from the position that a bribe includes the transfer of benefits and advantages not only of a material, but also of an immaterial nature;

- the concepts of foreign officials, bribery in favor of foreign officials, and persons exercising public functions in international organizations have not been introduced;

- the crime of laundering criminal proceeds, including through corruption, has not been introduced into the criminal law in the form in which it should be in accordance with international norms and standards;

- there are no standards for bringing to criminal responsibility for illegally enriching officials who do not have their own transparent sources, which the UN Convention focuses on;

- the law has formed a clear and comprehensive concept of criminal liability of corporate legal entities, which would provide for a set of balanced and effective sanctions in terms of preventing and countering corruption committed using the method of corporate intervention and mediation. The specified specific criminal sanctions should take into account the nature of the person's activity and its sphere of influence of a corporate legal entity, the consequences of committing a crime and be proportionate to the nature of the act being committed, have a wide preventive resonance. At the same time, the mechanism of criminal liability should be applied in the case of a crime committed by a person who has a certain position in the corporate management structure of a legal entity or there should be a lack of proper control by corporate officials;

- the provisions on active repentance in criminal legislation have not been fully evaluated in terms of their effect and impact on criminal liability in the commission of corruption crimes, and provisions have not been introduced that would exclude on this basis the evasion of criminal responsibility by persons in the commission of a number of crimes.

3. In 2014 Kazakhstan has adopted a new Criminal Code of the Republic, which entered into force on January 01, 2015 and since its adoption, we have been analyzing modern criminal anti-corruption legislation, which provided for a fairly wide range of innovations in the application of criminal liability for corruption, in particular:

- the chapter containing the components of corruption crimes is set out in a new edition, the composition of corruption crimes has been revised,

- definitions related to the grouping of corruption crimes were now concentrated in Article 3 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan, which brought some greater clarity to the legislator's understanding of their composition;

- the terminology was supplemented with new definitions of "organization and management functions", commercial and administrative functions", which were not previously defined at the legislative level, but were only interpreted within the framework of Supreme Court rulings;

- the definition of "a person holding a position in the system of power" was expanded, in particular, the

term "a person holding a civil position" was introduced instead of the previously existing "public official in a state agency"; in previous versions of the Criminal Code, these definitions were not disclosed and were subject to interpretation by judicial authorities;

- the list of persons holding important public office has been expanded; in particular, it includes members of Parliament and judges;

- the definition of "persons authorized to perform public functions" has been changed, indicating that they include persons who are civil servants according to civil service legislation;

- employees of the National Bank of the Republic of Kazakhstan and its agencies are additionally included in the number of persons who have a status similar to that of persons endowed with public functions;

- in addition, a number of changes were introduced in the approach to sanctions for corruption crimes;

- in the Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan in 2015, it was prohibited, in the case of criminal prosecution for corruption offenses, the application of provisions on conditional release, on exemption from criminal liability in the case of reconciliation with the victim, exemption from criminal liability in connection with the use of bail or in connection with the expiration of the statute of limitations for criminal liability.

A comparative analysis of the approach of the Republic of Kazakhstan to the formation of the foundations for the application of criminal liability for corruption actions with similar approaches applicable in international standards, in the norms of European states and the European Union as a whole allows us to identify the main differences, which to a greater extent indicate the need for further clarification and improvement of the legal concept of Kazakhstan. In order to get an idea, we will conduct a general analysis of the approach to the application of criminal liability for acts of corruption that has been formed in modern pan-European legislative doctrine and practice, based, among other things, on the experience of applying international standards established by the UN and the OECD.

1. International standards and the pan-European approach developed on their basis proceed from the fact that corruption manifestations should receive an adequate response and response measures in the form of the application, first of all, of criminal sanctions. Only the criminal law regulation of Russia will ensure an appropriate level of anti-corruption, both at the level of prevention and at the level of post-criminal response. This is due to the nature and degree of danger and seriousness of corruption acts, and their extremely negative impact on management processes and the state of the economy in the state and society. The criminal law approach provides the most adequate and effective measures in detecting, investigating and prosecuting corruption and those involved in it. But nevertheless, in Kazakhstan, along with the criminal-legal way of responding, there is also a system of administrative measures to respond to corruption. Right-wing systems that provide, among other things, such a way of responding, that is, through the application of administrative and legal sanctions, are generally recognized as sufficiently ineffective. Even if they are coupled or

combined with the application of criminal law prohibitions and measures, administrative and legal methods of influencing similar acts cannot constitute an adequate impact. Often they may compete or overlap with each other, administrative measures may give a false signal about the possibility of their application to acts that deserve more acute and harsh response measures, or their use may occur, including abuse by the officials themselves who use them, creating grounds for impunity for corrupt officials. That is, a vicious circle arises, among other things, when some persons commit acts of corruption, while others contribute to this to some extent. Thus, Kazakhstan is an example of a legal system in which, along with criminal liability, administrative liability can also be applied, which in general was also widely criticized in the Istanbul Action Plan applicable to Central Asian States, specially developed by the OECD during the monitoring of anti-corruption legislation of these countries. Based on the analysis carried out by the OECD during the monitoring of the development of Kazakh legislation, it is noted that in the legal system of Kazakhstan, no attempts have been made to eliminate all intersections, overlaps and inconsistencies, possible means for imposing criminal and administrative legal means of influencing corruption forms of manifestation.

2. The formation of criminal liability according to the idea of the creators of the UN Convention and European legislators for corruption crimes excludes the use of any double standards or standards related to the threshold establishment of criteria for classifying the same act as a crime or other acts of corruption, for example, acts prosecuted administratively. Although, in general, this issue is formulated abstractly and is at the discretion of the national legislator, but with a slightly different general wording given in the UN Convention and the CE Convention on Criminal Liability for Acts of Corruption. Thus, according to paragraph 1. of Article 30 of the UN Convention, each State party to the Convention undertakes obligations to introduce corruption offenses and establish responsibility for them in the form of sanctions commensurate with the seriousness and gravity of the crime. According to Articles 2 and 3 of the 1999 CE Convention, each party to the Convention must take appropriate legislative and other measures necessary to establish criminal liability, according to domestic legislation, for intentionally committing any actions related to active or passive corruption. That is, in the case of the CE Convention, we are talking about criminal liability, the same applies to the acts listed in articles 4-13 of the 1999 CE Convention. And only article 14 of the Convention refers to the establishment of criminal or other sanctions for the relevant acts. Thus, the European approach proceeds from the need to establish criminal liability for most of the corruption acts listed in the relevant Convention.

In Kazakhstan's practice and legal system today, there is still an approach that presupposes the establishment of two legal types of acts and the corresponding criminal and administrative responsibility, but separated by a certain threshold value, the boundary at which the act can become criminally punishable, pro-

vided that the amount of the alleged illegal benefit exceeds a certain threshold. The purpose of using such a system is an attempt to exclude the legal basis for bringing to criminal responsibility for less dangerous offenses, separated by a threshold criterion related to the amount of remuneration. But nevertheless, this approach does not meet the global standard that requires the application of criminal liability for any act in the field of corruption, regardless of the size of the illegal benefits received. The European and international approach presupposes the possibility of establishing different types of responsibility for various types of corruption acts, but not depending on the amount of remuneration received, respectively, it is assumed that in the Republic of Kazakhstan it is legitimate to consider not the application of the concept of the minimum threshold size of a criminal act, but the concept of a formal approach to its design features, which, if they are in combination, otherwise the situation develops, in which, outwardly, according to formal signs, the act manifesting itself as a crime can be qualified as an administrative offense as insignificant in its consequences. Nevertheless, Kazakhstan has retained in the Code of Administrative Offences after the 2014 reform the compositions of corrupt administrative acts that compete with the compositions of criminally punishable corruption. The Code of Administrative Offenses

retains chapter 34, which is called "Administrative corruption offenses", among which there are compositions that can be transferred to the plane of criminally punishable.

References

1. Convention on Criminal Liability for Corruption of Council of Europe, January 27, 1999
2. The UN Convention against Corruption, adopted in New York on October 31, 2003.
3. Human rights treaty bodies, contribution to the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, May 2016.
4. UN Commission on Human Rights, Progress report submitted by the Special Rapporteur, UN Doc. E/CN.4/Sub.2/2005/18, June 22, 2005, item 2. 41.
5. Istanbul Anti-Corruption Action Plan. A practical guide for monitoring experts. URL: <https://www.oecd.org/corruption/acn/IAP-Manual-Monitoring-Experts-RUS.pdf>
6. The Law of the Republic of Kazakhstan "On Combating Corruption" with amendments and additions as of 06.10.2020
7. Criminal Code of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated July 3, 2014 No. 226-In the SAM
8. Anti-corruption: new challenges. Monograph. / Ed. by T. Khabrieva. M., INFRA-M, 2016, p. 345.
9. Convention on Combating Bribery of Foreign Officials in International Commercial Transactions